

Attitude towards Sustainable Products among College Students in Madurai District

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Abstract

Now-a-days Young generations are eager to buy and consume sustainable products. The transformation among young consumer's attitudes due to the concern of social, economic, and environmental status has lead to a close connection to Sustainability. This rapid development of knowledge and awareness has influenced the younger generations towards sustainable production by observing the young generations it shows that they are concerned about the environmental effects of human beings in practice and they are moving towards sustainable products. Not only sustainable products, sustainability consumerism has also received increasing attention among young people in recent days. The aim of this paper to examine the factors that influence turning their attention towards sustainable products, such as price, quality, attributes, availability of the products and awareness etc., Based on these factors and opinion hypothesis are formulated, and convenience sampling techniques and structured questionnaires are used by the researcher to collect data.

Keywords: sustainable products, attitude, sustainability in consumerism

Introduction

Sustainable products are those that serve the needs of the environment and organic or green products to reduce environmental impact. Most of the time sustainable products have a basic rule of 7 R'S they must be reviewed, discarded, reduced, recycled, repaired, restored, recycled. These issues must be considered when manufacturing durable products. Nowadays, we care about the environment, the warming of the climate, health problems affect the buyer while decided to buy sustainable products. Therefore, Going Green is a trend that has expanded in the consciousness of young customers. Therefore, the main objective of this study is to find out the factors that influence and affect the attitude of the youth of Madurai

region towards sustainable products. Firstly, the literature review and conceptual framework was provided, secondly methodologies are explained which are applied on the study. Next part of the study is provided with result and discussion. After that conclusion and suggestions.

Review of Literature

(Unnamalai, 2016), he revealed that though the awareness and the usage of Green products among people are low. But most are conscious about the eco-friendly environment and try to save the earth from pollution. But most are conscious about the eco-friendly environment and try to save the earth from pollution. The Corporation is already creating a campaign for avoiding plastic products. The corporation, University, and other private companies try to use conservative energy. Join hands could take the steps from the government, corporations, NGOs, and Private companies.

(Chen, 2020), Indicates that consumers in developed countries generally have higher awareness and access to sustainable products compared it to those in developing countries. Additionally, younger generations tend to be more informed and proactive in seeking sustainable options.

(Harris, 2021), Revealed in his study that awareness of sustainable products has a direct impact on consumer behavior. Increased awareness often translates to higher demand for these products, encouraging businesses to adopt sustainable practices. Consumers are willing to pay a premium for products they perceive as environmentally friendly and ethically produced. However, there remains a segment of consumers who, despite being aware, do not prioritize sustainability in their purchasing decisions due to factors such as higher costs or perceived inconvenience.

Statement of the Problem

Towards sustainability has emphasized the importance of adopting sustainable practices in day-to-day life. This shift is critical in combating environmental degradation and promoting a healthier planet. Understanding their attitudes towards sustainable products is crucial for developing strategies that enhance sustainable consumption patterns. This research aims to explore and analyze the attitudes of college students in the Madurai district towards sustainable products. This focus will be identifying the factors that influence their attitudes,

the level of awareness and knowledge they possess about sustainability, and the barriers they face in adopting sustainable products among college students

Objectives of the Study

- ❖ To study the socio-economic background of the respondents.
- ❖ To analyze the awareness level of sustainable products.
- ❖ To identify the opinion of the respondent's attitude.
- ❖ To determine the factors which influence the respondent's attitude.

Research Methodologies

The present paper consists of both primary and secondary data. The primary data were collected by a survey method with structured questionnaires. The questionnaire was designed to know the attitude towards sustainable products among youngsters in Madurai District. The customers were selected through convenience sampling techniques and the sample size considered for the study is 100 respondents. The secondary data were taken from various books, published journals etc., the collected data were analyzed using SPSS. The statistical tools are percentage analysis, Rank test and Garrett ranking.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Following data are collected from the respondents, the researcher used to analyze the data and provide an interpretation.

Profile of the Respondents

After selecting and categorizing respondents based on gender, age, education level, family monthly income, family size, and location, the profile of those who use sustainable products was analysed.

Awareness about Sustainable Products

This paper aims to analyse the current state of awareness regarding sustainable products, the factors influencing this awareness, and the impact it has on college students and market trends.

Table 1: Profile of the Respondent

VARIABLES	CHARACTERISTICS	RESPONDENTS IN PERCENTAGE
Gender	Male	71
	Female	29
	Total	100
AGE	BELOW 20	37
	20-23	48
	24-25	15
	Total	100
Educational Qualification	U.G	56
	P.G	37
	Research Scholar	7
	Total	100
INCOME OF THE FAMILY	BELOW 20,000	42
	20,001-30,000	53
	Above 30,000	5
	Total	100
FAMILY SIZE	BELOW 3	48
	4-6	52
	ABOVE 6	Nil
	Total	100
LOCATION	Rural	85
	Urban	15
	Total	100

Source: primary data

Table 1 shows the profile of the respondents it reveals that majority of the respondents are male 71% of respondents are between the age group 20-23 years, 56% Of the respondents are completed their Under Graduate, 52% of the respondents having 4-6 members in their family, the majority of the month family income is 20,001-30,000 and most of the respondents 85% are belongs to rural area.

Table 2: Awareness about Sustainable Products

PARTICULARS	CHARACTERISTICS	RESPONDENTS IN PERCENTAGE
How did you know about sustainable products?	Advertisement	27
	Friends and relatives	35
	Social media	38
	Other specify	Nil
	Total	100
How long are you using sustainable products?	Below one year	32
	2-3 years	24
	4-5 years	36
	Above 5 years	28
	Total	100
Which sustainable products do you prefer?	Health care	43
	Home care	12
	Personnel care	30
	Other specify	15
	Total	100
How will you purchase sustainable products?	Physical store	36
	Online	64
	Other specify	Nil
	Total	100

Source: primary data

Table 2 shows about the level of awareness about sustainable products of the respondents it reveals that 38% respondents of respondents are aware through social media. And majority 43% percentage of respondents prefer health care products and personal care 30 %. 36% of the respondents they all using sustainable products between the group 4-5 years. 64% of respondents are buying through online.

Garrett Ranking Technique for Opinion about Sustainable Product.

Its used to rank the opinion about sustainable product among college students from this researcher identifies 10 opinion and asked the students to rank the opinion.

S.NO	STATEMENT	MEAN SCORE	AVERAGE	RANK
1.	Packaging of sustainable products are attractive	5756	57.56	I
2.	Sustainable Products Are Expensive	5675	56.75	II
3.	Sustainable Products Have More Health Benefit	5445	54.45	III
4.	Sustainable Products Are Good For The Environment	5325	53.25	IV
5.	sustainable products have a good brand image	5290	52.90	V
6.	Sustainable products offer better performance than conventional products	4997	49.97	VI
7.	Sustainable Products Are Not Widely Available In Market	4869	48.69	VII
8.	Absence of Research and Innovation of Sustainable products	4652	46.52	VIII
9.	Fails To Explore Transparency	4539	45.39	IX
10	Government Influencing the People to Buy Sustainable Products Through Promotional Activities	4256	42.56	X

Source: primary data

Table 3 The analysis reveals that while the attractiveness of packaging and perceived health benefits drive consumer preference for sustainable products, challenges such as high cost, limited availability, and the need for greater transparency and innovation must be addressed. Companies should focus on enhancing the visual appeal, reducing costs, and

improving the availability and performance of sustainable products. Additionally, increased investment in research and clearer communication about the benefits and production processes of sustainable products can help build consumer trust and market share.

Rank the Factors Influencing Buying Behaviour

Students are influenced by a variety of factors that affect their purchasing decisions. Understanding these factors is crucial for businesses aiming to enhance their market strategies. This analysis evaluates ten different factors affecting consumer preferences, ranked based on their mean scores.

Table 4: Rank the Factors Influencing Buying Behaviour

S.NO	STATEMENT	Mean	Rank
1	Attractive packaging	4.87	I
2.	Life Style Changes	4.86	II
3.	Availability of Sustainable Products	4.84	III
4.	Promotional Activities	4.78	IV
5.	Attributes of The Products	4.76	V
6.	Quality of The Product	4.69	VI
7.	Health Benefits	4.52	VII
8.	Brand image of the product	4.47	VIII
9.	Environmental Benefits	4.37	IX
10.	Price of The Product	4.35	X

Source: primary data

Table 4 shows that the mean score of attractive packaging is 4.87. This indicates that visual appeal and the product packaging design significantly affect consumers' purchase decisions and it secures Rank 1st. A mean score of 4.86 with lifestyle changes is the second most important factor, reflecting the growing consumer awareness and the shift towards products that align with their evolving lifestyles. Businesses must stay attuned to these changes to meet consumer demands effectively. Mean Score: 4.84 The high rank for sustainable products highlights the increasing consumer preference for environmentally

friendly and sustainable options. This trend underscores the importance of sustainability in product offerings.

Conclusion

This study revealed more about sustainable products and several key insights. The attractiveness of packaging for sustainable products is a significant driver of consumer preference, indicating that visual appeal is crucial. However, the high cost of these products remains a major barrier, suggesting a need for strategies to make sustainable products more affordable or to communicate their long-term value more effectively. Health benefits and environmental advantages are also important factors that influence consumer decisions, reflecting a growing awareness and preference for products that promote well-being and sustainability. Companies should emphasize these benefits in their marketing efforts. In summary, while sustainable products have significant potential to attract consumers, addressing the challenges of high costs, limited availability, and transparency is crucial. By focusing on these areas, businesses can better position themselves in the growing market for sustainable goods and contribute to a more sustainable future.

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